
THE DOCTRINE OF COPYRIGHT EXHAUSTION IN SOFTWARE UNDER INDIAN COPYRIGHT ACT: A CURSORY GLANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study provides that copyright exhaustion serves an important social function of reducing the cost of information costs. Without it, buyers will be required to waste time and resources inquiring about their ability to resell copyrighted work. Because resale rights are generally regarded as desirable by society, the law should ordinarily grant them to buyers. There are costs associated with copyright exhaustion. The major drawbacks included a decline in the incentives to innovate as well as a regressive distributive effect as a result of copyright exhaustion's restriction on some price discrimination methods. The breadth of copyright exhaustion should be determined by the balance of these benefits and costs. This study applies the doctrinal method and explores the preferred scope of copyright exhaustion. The study argues that the copyright owner should not be prevented from exercising control over the commercial importation of copyrighted work or distributions of digital work. However, copyright exhaustion should be restricted and the copyright should not be allowed to bypass it by including magic words in their standard-form agreements. The study will examine Article 14 of the Indian Copyright Act 1957 with Art. 30 of the copyright. The present study shall briefly examine the copyright law on the applicability of doctrine in Indian copyright jurisprudence.

Keywords: Exhaustion rule, Copyright infringement, copyright monopoly, software, and IP protection

Introduction:

The core principle of copyright exhaustion is known as the first sale doctrine, this doctrine states that once the copyright owner transfer ownership of copyright work he losses the ability to control over the future distribution of those copies and the buyer is free to transfer the copies as they please.¹ The notion of exhaustion is to restrict the IP owners from benefiting perpetually from reselling IP-based products. The IP owner loses his right once the IP product has been conveyed to the buyer and the buyer of the IP product can resale under the first sale doctrine.²

Ownership confers the right to sell, lend, lease or otherwise dispose of that copy under the first sale doctrine. This article addresses this challenge by reexamining the rationale for exhaust standards in the light of recent technological, legal, and economic advancements. It finds that copyright exhaustion is justifiable as a technique for lowering information costs in the copyrighted product's market.

Due to the rapid growth of the digital world applying this principle copies can be easily transmitted between the counties and the copyrighted work can be copied and distributed physically or digitally rapidly is challenging. This challenge is exacerbated because copyright exhaustion is theorized. The prevailing wisdom has accepted an appealingly simple explanation about the function of the copy ownership system for over a century.

The present study offers elements that courts and policymakers might examine in implementing exhaustion rules more flexibly in particular contexts, based on classic IP exhaustion doctrine rationales. In determining whether the distribution right was exhausted, the court had to determine whether downloading a copy of a computer program that is governed by a user license agreement may be regarded as a first sale. This rationale highlights the information problems that lack of copyright exhaustion and greater control of subsequent distribution may bring about in the market. Exhaustion applies only to software copies but not to other digital copies downloaded from the internet.

On the product side of the computer programs, the following are categories are available in the market: firstly, Propriety software is copyrighted and branded for commercial use and personal

¹ VIDYA-MITRA, EXHAUSTION OF IPRS (2015), <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VH62ApYsPRI> (last visited Feb 20, 2022)

² Aaron Perzanowski & Jason Schultz, *Copyright Exhaustion and the Personal Use Dilemma*, MINNESOTA LAW REVIEW 78

computer. Microsoft leads the segment with a wide range of competing players in the accounting, publishing, e-learning, banking, and other sectors. This software is usually available off the shelf and online orders are based on the license agreement.³

Shareware software is made available for a limited period of free use and after customer satisfaction is purchased through a license agreement. In this type of software, the free version is a limited version at the end of the period, designed to stop working and where the buyer has to choose to buy and register a user. The source code is copyrighted and the customer cannot change it for permanent use.

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Freeware software is made available that can be used by customers and those who are satisfied can pay a profit to the software owner and can distribute this software to others to try the same. The customer however is not able to sell the software as the copyrighted is still in the compiler and the sole right of the customer is to use and distribute it to others for free.⁵

Open software is open-source, where the recipient is free to change the source code and modify it according to his or her needs. The only condition is that the original author of their efforts as agreed in the sale, for instance, Linux is the most advanced of these software types.⁶

Software alternatively called the computer program is a creative work under IPR and qualifies for protection under IPR based on the value of its creativity –dubbed as literary work fall under the copyright regime for protection as intellectual property.⁷

A computer program is considered a literary work written down, recorded, or otherwise reduced to material form. Copyright exists in the software provided sufficient efforts or skills

³ V.C. VIVIEKANANDAN & G.S. SRIVIDHYA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS IN CYBER SPACE 46 (2005)

⁴ *Id.* at 47

⁵ *Id.* at 49

⁶ B.N. PANDEY, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS 87 (Faculty of Law, Banaras Hindu University) (2003)

⁷ *Id.* at 89

have been extended to give it a new and original character. The copyright Act, of 1957 did not refer to the term computer program. By the copyright Act 1984, the definition section 2 (o) has been amended and added to the computer program.

Genesis of Exhaustion Doctrine

The doctrine of exhaustion in IPR can be traced back to the work of German jurist Josef Kohler (1849) in Europe who remarked on the principles of the connection between the different acts of exploitation.⁸ According to this principle, legally recognized activities involving the economic exploitation of a patent are linked to the movement the invention is created and end up dictating the scope of all earnings a right holder may get from it. Other acts fall outside the scope of the legal entitlement and if the patent is deemed exhausted the right holder is not then entitled to any further profits.⁹

1. REWARD THEORY

The doctrine was recognized by the German court in the field of trademark law and copyright. The essential principle of the theory of reward which the right holder might earn by distributing copies of a copyrighted work or items identified by a trademark is fundamentally tied to the premise of the connection between distinct exploitation activities.¹⁰

2. FULL OWNERSHIP THEORY

According to this rationale, the exhaustion theory is to provide the purchaser with a copy of work that includes a bundle of rights normally assigned to property; once ownership of a copy is acquired, the owner is presumed to be entitled to exercise all rights associated with the legal status of the property.

3. MARKET AND LEGAL CERTAINTY PROTECTION THEORY

A third rationale for the exhaustion of IPR is based on the idea of protecting the market and legal certainty. Restricting right holders' control over distributed copies of work serves to protect legal and economic exchange and to prevent transaction costs that would arise if

⁸ Antoni RubiPuig, *Copyright Exhaustion Rationales and Used Software*, 21, 162 (2013)

⁹ *Id.* at 162

¹⁰ COPYRIGHT | ARTPATENT, <https://www.artpatent.eu/en/services/copyright/> (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

acquirers of a copy had to negotiate a new license or authorization every time they envisioned a new form of use for the copy.

In this context, a computer program's interoperability with hardware or other software may advocate a greater degree of right holder control over these prospective uses. The prospects of productive interaction with other products, or services suggest may be reasonable and socially desirable to extend the scope of the control that the right holder may continue exercising once the product has left their commercial sphere. More scope for modulating the effects of the exhaustion or for opting out of its legal regime should perhaps be provided.

International Exhaustion rule

The term exhaustion refers to the generally accepted principle in IP law that a right owner's exclusive right to control the distribution of protected item lapses after the first act of the distribution. Once the item has been put on the market by or with the consent of the right of the owner, the exclusive distribution right is exhausted (which is why the principle is referred to in some jurisdictions as the first sale doctrine.¹¹

For example, a copyrighted DVD or a patented mobile phone, one is then free to in addition to sell, transfer or otherwise distribute it without further authorization from the right holder. This entitlement does not, of course, affect any other exclusive rights the right holder may enjoy, for example, the right to authorize activities such as reproduction or communication to the public – so the entitlement to distribute a legitimately purchased CD does not in itself extend to an entitlement to make a reproduction or public performance of the recorded music.

While it is generally accepted that IPRs are exhausted within the jurisdiction where the first sale takes place outside the jurisdiction in question? The answer to this depends on whether the country applies a regime of national exhaustion or international exhaustion and thereby prevents or allows so-called “parallel importation.”

National exhaustion means that right owners' distribution rights are only considered exhausted once they put the protected item on the market in that country. Distribution rights would not be considered exhausted concerning protected items that were only put on the market in another

¹¹ ANTONY TAUBMAN & JAYSHREE WATAL, A HAND BOOK ON THE WTO TRIPS AGREEMENT 18 (Cambridge University Press) (2012)

country, so those right holders can still control the sale or import of such items into the first country. For example, in a country with a national exhaustion regime, copyrighted and related rights holders can prevent the importation into that country of DVDs that they have sold in other countries. Thus the parallel import of products first sold on other markets is illegal in a country with a national exhaustion regime.

In contrast, if a country has an international exhaustion regime, this means that the right owner's distribution right in that country is exhausted regardless of where the first act of distribution took place. Thus, right holders cannot use IPR to prevent the importation and sale of DVDs that they have sold in another country. Therefore, in countries with an international exhaustion regime for copyright and related rights, parallel imports are legal.

Note that the products, imported as parallel imports are not counterfeit or pirated goods, but genuine or original products that have been sold in other countries with the authorization of the right holder; they do not infringe IPRs in the country of origin.

An alternative approach is taken in some free trade areas (FTAs) or custom unions, namely national exhaustion: in this case the right holder's IPRs are exhausted once the first sale takes place anywhere within the specified region. It is generally understood that national exhaustion favors market segmentation as well as differential pricing, product differentiation, and different release dates, whereas international exhaustion facilitates parallel importation of the same product sold at lower prices in other countries. During the Uruguay Round Negotiations, members negotiated a text that left them considerable discretion as to how to regulate the question of exhaustion.¹²

Article 6 provides that, for the purposes of dispute settlement under the TRIPS agreement, nothing in the Agreement shall be used to address the issue of the exhaustion of intellectual property rights on the condition that the national and MFN treatment obligations are complied with.¹³ This proviso was clarified in the 2001 ministerial Declaration on the TRIPS Agreement and Public Health. It is confirmed that the effect of the TRIPS provisions relevant to exhaustion of IPRs was to leave each Member free to establish its regime for exhaustion without challenge,

¹² *Id.* at 18

¹³ *Id.* at 19

subject to the MF and national treatment provisions of Articles 3 and 4.¹⁴

Art. 6 of the TRIPS agreement does not define exhaustive continue during negotiations due to its impact on free trade¹⁵. WTO members can adopt any regime of exhaustion. WTO members decided to adopt a particular regime of exhaustion that cannot be challenged under the dispute settlement mechanism, However WTO members must provide National Treatment and Most Favoured Nation treatment to nationals of all WTO members. WTO members in implementing any regime of exhaustion cannot violate other provisions of the agreement.¹⁶

The Berne Convention for the protection of Literary and Artistic does not highlight this doctrine of exhaustion¹⁷ however the TRIPS agreement explicitly states that “*nothing in this agreement shall be sued to address the issue of the exhaustion of Intellectual property rights.*”¹⁸ Art. 11 TRIPS provides the rental right to the computer program. Indeed, copyright exhaustion can invalidate many price discrimination methods by making resale permissible. Specifically, legal systems differ in answering two questions: first, what transaction triggers exhaustion, and second in what way does exhaustion narrow the scope of the exclusive rights.¹⁹ While an authorized sale of copyrighted goods typically triggers exhaustion, an authorized in foreign countries may not. In countries that apply a regime called national exhaustion such as India. Only a domestic sale triggers exhaustion. In those jurisdictions, the copyright owner’s written permission is required to sell items that were first sold in another country. The copyright owners de facto receive an exclusive right over importation.²⁰

In other countries, those implement international exhaustion and finally regional exhaustion triggered by an authorized sale within a certain region. In Israel, after exhaustion, commercial renting is prohibited, but noncommercial lending by public libraries is allowed even without the compensation of the author.²¹

¹⁴ *Id.* at 19

¹⁵ TRIPS - ARTICLE 6 6, <http://www.cptech.org/ip/texts/trips/6.html> (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

¹⁶ WTO | INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY (TRIPS) - FACT SHEET - PHARMACEUTICALS - 2, https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/trips_e/factsheet_pharm02_e.htm (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

¹⁷ SUMMARY OF THE BERNE CONVENTION FOR THE PROTECTION OF LITERARY AND ARTISTIC WORKS (1886), https://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/ip/berne/summary_berne.html (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

¹⁸ WTO | INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY - OVERVIEW OF TRIPS AGREEMENT, https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/trips_e/intel2_e.htm (last visited Feb 15, 2022)

¹⁹ 2015-IPM-COPYRIGHT-EXHAUSTION.PDF

²⁰ PARALLEL IMPORTS AND COPY-RIGHT - INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY - INDIA, <https://www.mondaq.com/india/copyright/854562/parallel-imports-and-copy-right> (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

²¹ RubiPuig

The question is whether overcoming pricing discrimination in this way advances copyright law's purposes. Copyright exhaustion renders certain kinds of arbitrage legal which makes certain price discrimination practices difficult to sustain. However it does not completely price discrimination.. therefore, in some cases, copyright exhaustion does not cause sellers to charge a uniform price, on the other hand, it facilitates them to use a different kind of price discrimination scheme, one that cannot be defeated by resale.

Hence, there is no global consensus regarding the scope of copyright exhaustion in the USA after exhaustion (authorized sale), the owner of a copy is allowed to rent and lend it for any purpose, for-profit or not. On the other hand after exhaustion the holder of a copyrighted work (eg book or a CD is not allowed except for public libraries to lend copies for free as long as the copyright holder is compensated.

Discussion involved

A copyright owner codes a software program and sells a copy of it to a buyer. Several sets of legal rules govern this transaction. The transaction between the parties is a contract for the sale of goods; it triggers contract law, as well as parties, agreed to the terms. The transaction involves the transfer of ownership and possession of the copy governed by copyright law. Normally, upon the completion of the transaction for the sale of goods, the title to the goods passes to the Buyer. The buyer can do with them whatever he pleases, including transferring them to others.

However, when the goods in question are protected under the Intellectual Property rights, the nature of the transaction changes and buyers' rights are limited by exclusive right, and by default, these rights are not transferred to a buyer of an item protected under the IP Law. When an item is protected under copyright law, the exclusive rights, right to reproduce the goods and the right to distribute are involved.

The exclusive rights create tension between the law governing personal property and intellectual property. Hence the copyright law evolves with this tension and balances the conflicting interests through the doctrine of copyright exhaustion, which is also known as the

first sale doctrine.²²

The digital consumer makes numerous copies of purchased software. Transferring that CD onto a computer creates a least a copy. Back up the hard drive, and a second copy now exists. Give a copy to a friend or save it in Google derive, likewise creating several copies into existence. So, despite the ubiquity of such personal copying its legal status is unclear, the copyright owners while conceding that at least some personal use is lawful. Also suggest that it sometimes implicates their exclusive rights to reproduce, and distribute create derivative works.²³ On the other hand, the consumers and third-party facilitators of personal use claim that technologies enabled them to use lawfully. Generally, public opinion has embraced the principle that consumers are entitled to make personal use of their copies for non-commercial purposes.²⁴ TPersonaluse should not be suppressed. The personal use of copyrighted software yields a variety of benefits to consumers, inventors, and the copyright systems. It encourages the goals of copyright, to increase public access, preservation, and enjoyment of a work. It enhances economic efficiency through the reduction of transaction costs. It protects consumer expectations of autonomy and privacy and encourages innovation.

Similarly, personal use will help the copyright holders, by encouraging the consumer to purchase legitimate copies by increasing their value. Protecting the right holders under copyright bedrock assumptions incentivizes artistic creation.²⁵

Personal use is also beneficial to addressing copyright law's credibility crisis, closing the gap between the right holder's implication of law and the understanding of it.²⁶ Finally, personal use of copyright comports with our normative and historical understanding of personal property. Whereas the copyright owners control, their intangible IP rights, purchasers control the exclusive rights to the specific copy they buy.²⁷ Hence, the personal use creates the demarcation by giving the purchaser domain over the copy and the copyright holder control over the copyright. Despite, these arguments and widely held beliefs about the legitimacy of

²² DR. PETER DRAHOS, *THE UNIVERSALITY OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS: ORIGINS AND DEVELOPMENT* (University of London) (2012)

²³ Perzanowski & Schultz at 2069

²⁴ Perzanowski & Schultz

²⁵ Guy A Rub, *REBALANCING COPYRIGHT EXHAUSTION*, 64 *EMORY LAW JOURNAL* 79, 788

²⁶ Perzanowski & Schultz at 2068

²⁷ *Id.* at 2070

personal use, the doctrinal rationale for deciding that such an act is non-infringement has remained elusive.²⁸

Generally, Software can be protected under legal or technological means. Software protection under technological means of protection is practical for a certain niche and high-end software packages where additional costs of protection could be justified. This kind of protection is not considered effective as the technology itself can be used to defeat any protection that it may provide. The Laws of IPR provide the legal means for the protection of software. Under copyright, there are significant ways to protect software.²⁹

Exhaustion of Copyright in India

In India, the original software program is automatically getting copyright protection when the program is written and saved on a hard drive, floppy disk, or by running a printing list. The copyright of software only protects against the unauthorized copying of like program source code, object code, etc. Basically, under copyright law, the expression of ideas in the software can be protected not the mere idea in the software.³⁰ Determine what does constitute the expression of an idea and what an idea in the software is crucial in the protection of software under copyright law.³¹

Section 14 did not specify the regime of exhaustion as originally enacted in 1957. Penguin Book. Interpreted section 51^{32,33} to prohibit importation of copies into India for selling. Even though there is no specific right to import granted under Section 14 of the Copyright Act 1957. Court interpreted the work published in 14(a) (ii) to include the (importation where rights are exhausted internationally). 1994 amendment to section 14(1) (a) (ii)³⁴ to issue copies of the work to the public not being copies already in circulation. The problem with the amendment does not define the territoriality of sale whether national or international.

²⁸ Rub at 792

²⁹ B.N. PANDEY, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS 135 (Faculty of Law, Banaras Hindu University) (2003)

³⁰ Pranesh Prakash, *Exhaustion: imports, Exports, and the doctrine of first sale in Indian Copyright law*, 30, 638 (2012)

³¹ at 138

³² THE COPYRIGHT ACT, 1957 (14 OF 1957).PDF,

³³ SECTION 51 IN THE COPYRIGHT ACT, 1957, <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1038145/> (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

³⁴ SECTION 14(A) IN THE COPYRIGHT ACT, 1957, <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/56089611/> (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

Penguin case:³⁵ the plaintiff entered into an agreement with the copyright owner about printing and publishing, and the defendant imported the goods from those countries offering books. The plaintiff infringed the copyright. The court interpreted section 51.

Post Penguin decision raised many issues interpreted 51(b) (4) read with 2(m) India following national exhaustion to first sale doctrine. It is not territorial but national exhalation but the court did not recognize the importance of section 14 amendment.

Eureka International v. India Book distributor Ltd. (2005)³⁶ Bombay High court the ration of Penguin followed the court did not acknowledge the importance of the amendment and the question of what constitutes importation of an infringing copy under section 51(b) (iv).³⁷

Since 1984 the Copyright Act protects the software. In 1994 law was amended to provide explicit protection to software and database under the definition of literary works.³⁸ Under the copyright (Amendment Act, 1999) the following acts have been declared as non-infringing acts;

- a) *Obtaining information that is required for the interoperability of an independent computer program but is not otherwise easily available.*
- b) *The process of observing, studying, or testing the operation of a computer program to identify the concepts and principles that underpin it.*
- c) *Making copies or adapting a computer program for non-commercial home use from a lawfully obtained copy.*

The basic rule of copyright law is to protect the exclusive right of the owner of the copyright over the copyrighted work about distribution sale etc. However, his right will be exhausted

³⁵ CASE ANALYSIS: PENGUIN BOOKS LTD. V INDIA BOOK DISTRIBUTORS AND ... NITI MANTHAN, <http://nitimanthan.in/blog-posts/blog-niti-manthan/case-analysis-penguin-books-ltd-v-india-book-distributors-and-others/> (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

³⁶ EUROKIDS INTERNATIONAL PVT. LTD. VS INDIA BOOK DISTRIBUTORS EGMONT ... ON 5 AUGUST, 2005, <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1976989/> (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

³⁷ Prakash at 637

³⁸ COPYRIGHT PROTECTION FOR COMPUTER SOFTWARE AN INDIAN PROSPECTIVE - INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY - INDIA, <https://www.mondaq.com/india/copyright/262564/copyright-protection-for-computer-software-an-indian-prospective> (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

when the first sale of copyrighted work is made. The subsequent sale or redistribution of the copyrighted work is not an infringement of copyright.

Supreme Court of India in the case of *Engineering Analysis Centre For Excellence Pvt Ltd v. CIT*³⁹ The aforementioned case involved the issue of Tax and copyright deals with the End User License Agreement (EULA) of the software. The court recognized the doctrine of exhaustion in software. It held that EULAs were not licensed under section 30 of the Copyright Act, 1957. As the foreign companies did not transfer any right under section 14 (a) or 14(b) of the Act to the Indian distributors. It was held that the payment made by the Indian companies for using software developed by foreign companies would not amount to “royalty” which is taxable in India. The supreme court has highlighted EULAs that allow end-users to use software but do not transfer or exhaust any right provided under sections 14(a) or 14(b).

The Supreme Court of India, in the recent case, has held that money paid by the Indian companies for the use of computer software developed by foreign companies is not deemed “royalty.” The court established the doctrine of copyright exhaustion in software and opined on copyright concerns relating to End User License Agreements (EULA) held that the amount paid is taxable income in India.

Similarly, the Delhi High court agrees that the amount paid for the software does not amount to royalty. In contrast, the Madras High court and Karnataka High Court have adopted a different position.

Section 14 (b) (ii) of the copyright has been amended twice. The first amendment 1994 to section 14(b) (ii) created an exception to the doctrine of copyright exhaustion in software. However, the amendment 1999 to the said section reestablished the doctrine of exhaustion, and section 14(b) (ii) is a very precise provision in respect of computer programs.

Section 52(1) (aa) to (ad) deals with reverse engineering of software for a specific purpose. It has been argued that engaging in reverse engineering does not lead to copyright infringement. However, Law regarding EULAs is unclear and can limit the fair dealing provisions.⁴⁰

³⁹ LL 2021 SC 124

⁴⁰ SUPREME COURT RECOGNISES DOCTRINE OF COPYRIGHT EXHAUSTION IN SOFTWARES, AND ITS SUBSERVIENCE TO EULAS SPICYIP, <https://spicyip.com/2021/03/supreme-court-recognises-doctrine-of-copyright-exhaustion-in-softwares-and-its-subservience-to-eulas.html> (last visited Feb 28, 2022)

In the case, Santhosh VG⁴¹ was the defendant running video paler and rental services, the defendant renting CD DVDs which lawfully were sold in India. The defendant used to import and sell in India in the rental fee. The plaintiff which is a leading Film Company in the USA alleges the defendant has no rental license in his favor. The defendant's actions amount to infringement under Section 14 (d) (2) read with Section 51 of the Indian Copy Right Act. Defendant content died that his sale is based on the first sale doctrine. The doctrine would apply to CD DVDs and he is legally authorized to sell them. Section 14(2)(m) incorporates the first sale doctrine under the Indian Copyright Act. Copy is not in circulation is not first sale doctrine.

The Court recognized copyright exhaustion in computer software by observing primarily two amendments to the Copyright Act, 1957 made in the year 1994 and 1999, where it opined that the latter amendment re-established the doctrine of copyright exhaustion in software in section 14 (b) (ii).

The Sale of the property is the evidence of transferring the ownership. Generally, property vendors will not impose an absolute condition on the sale of the property on the right to use in the land and chattel.⁴² Similarly, the same principles have been emphasized in the Indian Sale of Goods, it reads “*No absolute condition on sale can be.*”⁴³ Likewise, no absolute condition on sale can be attached to the buyer to enjoy the property peacefully. Similarly, it extends to Intellectual property owners. IP owner loses distribution control on any product embedding Intellectual property.

To, legitimize personal uses, courts and commentators have commonly adopted the narrow interpretations of exclusive rights, fair use, and implied license. While each approach can resolve some aspect of the personal use dilemma. This is practical in the circumstances where personal use is challenged in the context of secondary liability claims rather than direct infringement against individual users, in which courts frequently draw broad inferences about personal use rather than making individual judgments of specific users.

Personal use Justification

Personal use can improve public access to works, as well as enjoyment and preservation. It also

⁴¹ *Warner Bros. Entertainment Inc. and Ors. v. Santosh V. G., CS (OS) No. 1682/2006,*

⁴² VIDYA-MITRA

⁴³ *Section 19(1) and (2) of Sale of Goods Act 1930, in SALE OF GOODS ACT, 1930*

protects the privacy and liberty of consumers. It enhances creativity, transactional clarity, and respect for the copyright system. Ensuring public access, enjoyment, and preservation of works is among copyright law's primary aims.

Personal use is unregulated

Copyright owner has limited, not plenary rights. Many personal uses are simply outside the scope of those statutory rights. For instance, singing in the shower or quietly reading a novel is both lawful, but they are not covered by any copyright provisions.

Furthermore, certain personal uses are exceptions to typically applicable exclusive rights. These include the adaptation or backup of a computer program, as well as the transfer of presentation of a particular copy of a work. The copyright law distinguishes between public and private uses, most notable in the contexts of an exhibition of performance and distribution.

However, this socially desirable aim must be balanced against the decrease in incentives to innovate, as well as the possibility of a regressive distributive impact caused by copyright exhaustion. The scope of copyright exhaustion should be determined by this balancing. Another alternative reason for the concept is likewise dismissed as unconvincing or irrelevant in this study.

Personal use as Fair use

Fair use emerges in common law as an equitable defense to copyright infringement, allowing for uses that would serve some socially beneficial purpose despite the copyright owner's right to exclude them.

Personal use as impliedly License

The court has recognized an implied license for both the copyright owner and the consumer intended for a work to be used for a certain purpose, such as when an architect draws up designs and provides them to a homeowner. This principle is beneficial to consumers who can avail of cheaper versions of already sold products in the international market and International exhaustion of IP is beneficial to developing countries to get IP products at the cheapest price. However, there are certain points against this principle that IP owners discouraged price discrimination, discouraged post-sale service by local vendors, and encourage price arbitrage

and free movement of goods.

Exceptions to the first sale are as follows right (Films, sound recording, and computer program)

- a) *Droit de suite* (Right to follow) concerning the original copy of the copyrighted work
- b) Contractual restraints of certain types

Conclusion:

Every legal system has rules regarding *regex* exhaustion, which in turn limits the scope of the exclusive rules governing exhaustion substantially differ among legal systems. Exhaustion of IP rights reduces the transaction costs associated with the need to check the idiosyncratic properties of products that incorporated copyrighted works. Exhaustion thus protects certainty in legal and economic exchanges of a new license with the copyright holder or the risks generated by hold-up problems associated with the right holders' interest in demanding a greater share of the profits or extracting them all.

Many software developers believe that in the case of copyright, the competitors can readily discern the underlying – unprotected ideas and replicated these without the necessity to engage in literal copying of any of the code used in the original. For instance, rewriting the computer program from one language into a different language and copying the source or object code is an infringement of copyright if the plot of the playbook is copied. The same principle is applied to computer software protection as well.

However, the consumers have the benefit of the first sale doctrine only concerning the purchased product in question. No copies can be made as a defense under the first sale doctrine. We apply the theory of exhaustion to both digital and non-digital personal use as space-shifting tangible media storing personal media via cloud computing and jailbreaking personal electronics, to demonstrate how courts can resolve such disputes in the digital era elegantly and equitably. In this doctrine, currently codified section of 14(a) (ii) copyright Act, the owner of a copy of his protected work (e.g a book or a CD) has the right to transfer that copy to others. This doctrine significantly weakened the control that copyright owners enjoy over the distribution of their works.

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